

NEWA Open-Source Model-Chain v1.0 Deliverable D3.5

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	ii
Executive Summary	iii
Introduction	1
1. Intended Use	1
2. Modeling Scope.....	1
3. License.....	2
4. CFDWind3 OpenFOAM library	2
4.1. Overview	2
4.2. Code structure.....	3
4.3. Installation/Compiling	5
4.4. Tutorial Test Cases	6
5. Outlook.....	7
References	7
Acknowledgements.....	10

Executive Summary

This report provides a brief user's manual for the first release of the NEWA open-source model-chain. The document is associated to a public git repository that will be updated throughout the rest of the project.

The objective of this release is to allow early-adopters of the model-chain to start testing the open-source code and, eventually, provide feedback to the NEWA developers about usability, possible bugs, robustness, etc.

The repositories consist of:

- CFDWind3 OpenFOAM libraries to run atmospheric-boundary layer microscale simulations driven by mesoscale inputs. Tutorial test case based on the GABLS3 diurnal-cycle benchmark. Repository available at:

<https://github.com/iat-cener/CFDWind>

Additional test cases will be added in the future as new benchmarks are produced based on the experiments of the project.

The report provides an overview of the model-chain context and its intended use followed by a description of CFDWind3 libraries. Finally, an outlook on future developments is provided.

Introduction

The New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) aims at producing a more reliable characterization of wind resources across Europe through a high resolution wind atlas and an experimental database that will lead to a significant reduction of uncertainties. Experimental campaigns of unprecedented scale and coverage have been conducted to map a wide range of terrain and wind conditions (Mann et al., 2017). This is the basis for the development of a model chain that blends relevant atmospheric scales from mesoscale to microscale. The modeling scope is limited to the characterization of external wind conditions (Petersen and Troen, 2012), leaving wind turbine wake modeling out of the program.

The model-chain efforts are directed to determining the range of applicability of meso-micro methodologies suitable to address end-user needs from the spatial planning to the site assessment phases (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2016a). To this end, an “ambidextrous” verification and validation (V&V) strategy is established to combine flow cases, suitable for targeted model development objectives, with long-term integrations of annual wind conditions, suitable to assess the added value of these developments in terms of end-user quantities of interest such as annual energy production, turbulence intensity, wind shear, etc. A hierarchy of benchmarks is defined to guide this V&V program using the experimental database generated in the project (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2016b).

1. Intended Use

This first release of the NEWA model chain is a beta version open to the public domain for testing and feedback. The intention is to engage with early-adopters that can start using the code alongside the validation program. This will allow them to evaluate the potential of introducing the model in their wind assessment applications. To this end, the validation benchmarks of the project are open to internal and external participants of the project willing to test the NEWA model chain.

As new changes are introduced, as a result of the model evaluation process, it will be possible to track these changes throughout the project with quantitative information about added performance on the reference model and how other models (more or less advanced) compare to this benchmark. By sharing the source code of the reference model together with the validation datasets and evaluation scripts, it is possible to improve the traceability and transparency in the assessment and development of state-of-the-art models.

2. Modeling Scope

The ultimate goal of this open-source release is to provide a reference flow model that can link mesoscale and microscale wind climate conditions consistently. The mesoscale part of the model-chain is based on the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF, Skamarock et al., 2008) model, version 3.6.1, based on the European wind atlas configuration (Hahmann et al., 2017).

The microscale model released in this repository is part of CENER's CFDWind3 model which, in turn, is built under the open-source CFD-toolkit OpenFOAM version 2.4.0 (The Open FOAM Foundation, 2018). The model is driven by large-scale forcing terms (so called tendencies in WRF) produced by the mesoscale model. These tendencies are obtained in the standard output of WRF following the method described in Lehner (2018a,b). This meso-micro methodology can be tested on the GABLS3 diurnal-cycle benchmark (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2017a, 2018), for which configuration files are provided.

3. License

WRF is developed by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) and released with a public domain license, which means that the code can be used by any person or entity for any purpose without any fee or charge. The source code shall be downloaded from NCAR's WRF Model User's Page (2018) website.

CFDWind3 is published under the GNU General Public License version 3.0., inherited from the OpenFOAM license. This requires anyone distributing the code or a derivative work to make the source available under the same terms, and also provides an express grant of patent rights from contributors to users (GNU Operating System, 2017). The source code shall be downloaded from the OpenFOAM Foundation (2018) website.

4. CFDWind3 OpenFOAM library

4.1. Overview

CFDWind3 is a tool developed at CENER for the simulation of atmospheric flows. The current system is built under the open-source Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) toolkit OpenFOAM version 2.4.0.

The model is designed to solve the unsteady Reynolds Navier-Stokes equations (URANS) for incompressible flows in which turbulence closure is achieved by using eddy-viscosity theory and the modified (two-equation) k-Epsilon closure scheme proposed by Sogachev et al. (2012).

The solver is based on the Boussinesq approximation by including a buoyancy term in the momentum equations which, together with the solution of the energy-transport equation and additional source/sink terms in the turbulence closure, allows simulating the evolution of the diurnal cycle. On the other hand, only dry air is considered so neither humidity transport equation nor heat transfer by radiation or phase changes are included.

The Boussinesq approximation for incompressible flow is approached in OpenFOAM through the *buoyantBoussinesqPimpleFoam* solver which introduces the PISO-SIMPLE algorithm to solve the pressure-velocity-temperature coupling. This algorithm does not solve the continuity equation; instead, it solves a pressure Poisson equation that

enforces continuity. Details about the solver algorithm for OpenFOAM can be found in OpenFOAM-PISO (2014).

The original OpenFOAM solver is modified following the method proposed by Sanz-Rodrigo et al. 2017b. Besides the Coriolis force, large-scale forcing is introduced as source terms in the microscale simulation by extracting from WRF the momentum and energy budget (so called tendencies) associated to the pressure gradient and the advection of momentum and temperature. To avoid double-counting of terrain effects that are explicitly modeled by the microscale simulation, the tendencies are averaged horizontally to obtain a column model that is time and height dependent but is uniform across the microscale domain. A sensitivity analysis on the selection of an appropriate averaging length scale can be found in Chavez-Arroyo et al. (2018). CFDWind has adopted the same approach as SOWFA (Churchfield et al. 2014), also based on OpenFOAM, to incorporate tendencies as source terms.

The surface conditions comply with the Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory (MOST) for neutral-stability condition as proposed by Richards & Hoxey (1993) and Parente et al. (2011). These conditions are applied as wall functions to the fields of eddy-viscosity η_t , kinematic thermal conductivity α_t , turbulence dissipation ε , and Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE).

So far, it has been found only small variations in the results obtained when including stability functions in the turbulence fields, namely α_t and η_t . Therefore, in this release, only mesoscale Dirichlet conditions are prescribed for the variations of temperature at the ground, which are introduced through a wall temperature flux field that uses the algorithm proposed by Basu et al. (2008) to account for the atmospheric stability in the surface layer. To this end, as in SOWFA, the dynamic values of velocity and temperature scales are computed based on the local flow, consistent with MOST and using stability functions (Etling, 1996).

4.2. Code structure

CFDWind3 consist of the following list of OpenFOAM libraries and applications that can be easily compiled via the *Allwmake* file, once the proper environmental variables of OpenFOAM2.4.1 are loaded. The general folder's structure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Folder's structure of CFDWind3.

a) Applications

1) Solvers

- *ABLSolver*: Main solver for atmospheric boundary layer turbulent flow. Built on top of *ABLSolver* from SOWFA project, which in turn is based on the OpenFOAM *buoyantBoussinesqPimpleFoam* solver. It includes Coriolis and tendencies forcing with the functionality of including surface roughness, stability and wind speed and direction. As in SOWFA, so far it can only handle structured hexahedral meshes and flat terrain sites.

2) Utilities

- *setRANSfieldABL*: Departs from the *setFieldsABL* from SOWFA modified to initialize the flow field in the RANS simulations. It specifies the initial profile of velocity and temperature based either on height-dependent tables, logarithm profile or geostrophic values. Turbulence fields, namely *TKE* and ϵ are prescribed following an Ekman layer approach.
- *writeCellCoordinates*: A utility to write in *txt* format the *x,y,z* coordinates of the *internalField* and all patches. Useful for creating the inputs for tools or programs outside the OpenFOAM classes environment.

b) Libraries

1) Incompressible/turbulenceModels: Contains custom boundary conditions based on SOWFA system:

- *specifiedSurfaceTemperatureq2*: surface temperature flux / heating - Specify a surface cooling/heating rate and the appropriate temperature flux is calculated.
- *timeVaryingMappedFixed* value with inlet outlet. Useful when WRF results are also applied as inlet boundary conditions.

2) Incompressible/RAS:

- *kEpsilonSogachevPrecursor*. a modified version of OpenFOAM standard *kEpsilon* model which now include *Pr_t* and *nu_t* dependent on atmospheric stability as proposed by Sogachev et al. 2012 and Koblitz et al. 2013.
- *derivedFvPatchFields/wallFunctions*: wall functions to comply with MOST for *nu_t* and *epsilon* as in Parente et al (2011). Although their current implementation only considers neutral stability, it has been tested that very small differences in the results are obtained when extended stability-based MOST functions are included.

4.3. Installation/Compiling

Once OpenFOAM is installed and CFDWind3 downloaded, you should follow these steps:

- 1) Make sure you have loaded the OpenFOAM v2.4.1 environment.
- 2) Change directory to the CFDWind3 local directory
- 3) Run `./Allwclean`.
- 4) Run `./Allwmake`.
- 5) Make sure that no error messages appeared and that all libraries and applications are listed as "up to date."

Even though the example case is preconfigured with the forcing files required to run the tutorial, external libraries of *netCFD* and *Python* programming language are needed if the user wants to modify the pre-processing and, in particular for post-processing the OpenFOAM outputs to replicate/analyze/share the results in the format required in the benchmarking process <http://windbench.net/gabls-3>.

netCFD4 system libraries, as well as its Python bindings are available in most Linux-based OS repositories. In the specific case of Debian-type systems you can install them as follows:

- 1) Install *netCDF* system libs:
>> `sudo apt install ibnetcdf-dev netcdf-bin`
- 2) Install (or make sure you have) systems libs:
>> `sudo apt install build-essential`
- 3) Install (or make sure you have) *pip* library management system:
>> `sudo apt install python-pip`
- 4) Make sure *pip* is updated
>> `pip install --upgrade pip`
- 5) Install *netCDF4* python bindings
>> `pip install netCDF4`

The scripts are known to work with Python v2.7 which, in addition, requires the following specific Python libraries (and version):

- matplotlib (1.5.1)
- netCDF4 (1.2.9)
- numexpr (2.6.3)
- numpy (1.14.0)

- pandas (0.22.0)
- pip (9.0.1)
- scipy (1.0.0)

4.4. Tutorial Test Cases

Tutorial test cases are included in the “example cases” folder. So far only one case is included (GABLS3), but the list will be growing as new benchmarks from the NEWA experiments and other cases from external contributions are carried out.

- **GABLS3:** Diurnal cycle driven by mesoscale data:

This site is part of the Cabauw Experimental Site for Atmospheric Research (CESAR) in the Netherlands. The example is taken from the benchmark initiative of the third GEWEX Atmospheric Boundary Layer Studies (GABLS3) case, revisited for wind energy applications (Sanz-Rodrigo et al. 2017a).

The inter-comparison study aimed to benchmark different meso-microscale coupling strategies with different turbulence-closure fidelity of the underlying microscale models.

The example case follows an “open-science” approach presented in Sanz-Rodrigo et al. (2017a) around the benchmark described in:

<http://windbench.net/gabls-3>.

with the results were published in:

<http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/854/1/012037>

The terrain is flat with laterally periodic boundaries. Due to these conditions and given the RANS approach, the case can be seen as a horizontally-homogeneous case. Thus only a 4x4x200 cells are needed to solve the 1D-type of problem, though mesh configuration can be selected in the *./inputParameters* file.

As described in the benchmark description (<http://windbench.net/gabls-3>), the mesoscale input data file, *GABLS3_tendencies_d02_YSU_w60_L9000.nc* can be downloaded at:

<https://b2share.eudat.eu/records/22e419b663cb4ffca8107391b6716c1b>

The contents of the GABLS3 folder are illustrated below. A description is made for the folders “additional” to the typical openFOAM structure.

Figure 2. Schematic with the folder structure of the GABLS3 tutorial.

To run the tutorial:

In order to run the GABLS3 example case you can follow the next steps:

- 1) Change directory to the GABLS3 folder
- 2) Download the tendencies input file (see <http://windbench.net/gabls-3>). So far the preprocessing scripts consider this file to be located in `./inputData/`. If you want to change the directory then edit the new path in the `./runPreprocessing.sh` scrip (`tendenciesFile` variable)
- 3) Edit the number of processors to use
- 4) Run the `./runPreprocessing.sh` script to set up the mesh and initial fields.
- 5) Run the `./runCase.sh` script
- 6) Run the `./runPosprocessing.sh` script to extract the results.

5. Outlook

This repository will be updated throughout the rest of the NEWA project as new features are added. Additional configuration files will be also added to the repository as new benchmarks are conducted during the validation program. These updates will be documented directly on the git repository with a final version released by the end of the NEWA project.

Exploitation plans for the open-source model-chain will be discussed during the last year of the project. In particular, the feasibility of establishing a community model will be analyzed to support a sustainable development and validation after the end of the project.

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